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A LEGAL EXAMINATION OF THE PAY-AS-YOU-EARN TAX SYSTEM IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Tax, no doubt, is the soul of any state, acting as a fundamental instrument through which governments generate revenue to constitutional responsibilities. In a country such as Nigeria the need for sustainable economic development, public service delivery, and infrastructural transformation is particularly urgent, the significance of a functional and equitable tax system cannot be overemphasized. Within this basic conceptual structure, the Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) tax system stands out as an essential mechanism for the assessment and collection of personal income taxes, specifically from individuals in formal sector employment. Created to ensure convenience, certainty and regularity in tax collection, the PAYE tax system requires that employers should deduct from source applicable taxes from employees' monthly earnings and remit them directly to the appropriate tax authorities. The PAYE tax system not only facilitates steady government revenue inflow, but also plays an important role in promoting voluntary compliance and reducing the risk of tax evasion among wage earners. Nevertheless, the implementation of the PAYE system in Nigeria has not been without significant structural and administrative problems. Challenges such as inconsistencies in statutory provisions, delays or failures in remittance by employers, lack of internet connectivity, limited oversight capacity of tax authorities, lack of transparency in tax assessments, and poor taxpayers' education have all collectively undermined the effectiveness of the PAYE system. In addition, disparities in the application of PAYE across federal and state jurisdictions in Nigeria raise concerns about the fairness, uniformity, and adherence to constitutional principles especially with respect to the taxing powers of different tiers of government. The aim of this study is to critically review the Pay-As-You-Earn tax system in Nigeria. In carrying out the study, doctrinal research methodology was employed by the researchers, utilizing primary sources such as the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Personal Income Tax Act, and relevant case laws. Secondary sources such as textbooks, law journals, and scholarly articles, were also all examined. The researchers found that while the Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) system remains a vital and crucial mechanism for personal income tax collection in Nigeria, its effectiveness is hindered by legal ambiguities, administrative inefficiencies, inconsistent enforcement, and limited taxpayer awareness. The researcher recommended, among others, legal reform, improved oversight on the part of tax authorities, capacity-building for tax administrators, and awareness creation and taxpayer education to enhance voluntary compliance and transparency in the system.

1. Introduction

The Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) system otherwise called Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG), is very essential, playing a crucial role in ensuring and enhancing the efficiency and transparency of tax collection from individuals.¹ The PAYE tax

¹ JC Dariye and others, 'Effect of Tax Revenue and Statutory Allocation on Fiscal Sustainability of States in Nigeria - Paye Tax Revenue Perspective' International Journal of Innovation Research and Advanced Studies (2024) 6(2), 55-68.

system operates in a mechanical manner, deducting income tax automatically from an employee's salary or wages, thereby making it easier for both employees and governments to comply with tax obligations.² With the Pay-As-You Earn tax system, there is therefore no need for individuals to file taxes at the end of the fiscal year, thus simplifying the whole process and ensuring that tax payments are made regularly.³ The system, by automatically withholding taxes at the point of income generation, reduces the likelihood of tax evasion, ensuring steady cash inflow for the government, and helps in the smooth operation and running of the national economy.⁴ The progressive nature of the Pay-As-You-Earn system, ensures that individuals pay taxes in proportion to their earnings, fostering equity and fairness in the tax process.

In Nigeria, the PAYE system has become the chief cornerstone of the nation's tax administration, serving as one of the primary sources of government revenue⁵. The system is critical and germane to Nigeria's economic growth, as it ensures consistent tax collection, particularly from formal sector employees who are actually the backbone of the country's workforce. It also reflects a broader commitment to social and economic fairness by linking individuals' tax obligations and responsibilities to their income levels⁶. The Pay-As-You-Earn system enhances a sense of collective responsibility among the populace, encouraging citizens to contribute to national development in a manner that aligns with their financial capacity⁷.

The PAYE system in Nigeria has undergone various reforms over the years, aimed at improving its efficiency, broadening the tax base, and enhancing compliance. However, despite the crucial and all-important role the Pay-As-You-Earn Tax system plays in Nigeria's tax collection and tax administration, its implementation and/or enforcement has been bedeviled with numerous problems. The challenges and/or problems range from statutory inconsistency, lack of internet facility, inadequate or poor enforcement mechanisms, and poor taxpayer education, to issues of lack of transparency in tax assessment and non-compliances by both employers and employees⁸. Furthermore, the PAYE tax system has been heavily criticized for its manifest inefficiency due to the fact that numerous employees do not fully grasp or understand how their tax liabilities are calculated, leading mistrust in the system⁹.

It is against this backdrop, therefore, that this research examined the PAYE system in Nigeria, evaluating its effectiveness in achieving its goals of tax compliance and revenue generation in the court.

2. History of Pay-As-You-Earn System in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the origin of the Pay-As-You-Earn system can be traced to when Personal Income Tax (PIT) (otherwise regarded as Pay-As-You-Earn) was introduced in the Northern parts of Nigeria in 1904 via the Native Revenue Ordinance Act of 1904 which later was extended to the Southern Protectorate by Lord Lugard now Western and Eastern regions¹⁰. The Ordinances were later consolidated and incorporated into the Direct Taxation Ordinance¹¹, forming the foundation of Nigeria's modern tax system. It was the need to tax personal incomes that gave birth to the enactment of the Income Tax Management Act (ITMA)¹², of which several amendments were made to the Act in

² KV Heden, 'The Pay-As-You-Earn Tax on Wages' <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/nft/1998/tlaw/eng/ch15.pdf> Accessed 10th April, 2025.

³ Ibid.

⁴ IU Asomba, JT Owu and CJ Onyinye, 'Effect of Tax Evasion and Avoidance on Economic Development of Grassroots in Nigeria' *Journal of Policy and Development Studies* (2023) 14(2), 11-23.

⁵ U.J. Onaiwu and E.L. Arekhandia, 'An Assessment of PAYE System of Taxation in Nigeria (TETFUND Sponsored)' *International Journal of Reserach and Innovation in Social Science* (2021) 5(11), 760-768.

⁶ A.E. Osho, "The Effect of Pay-As-You-Earn on Social and Economic Development in Nigeria' *Journal of Business and Management* (2020) 22(a), 57-65.

⁷ Ibid

⁸ U.J. Onaiwu and E.L. Arekhandia, 'An Assessment of PAYE System of Taxation in Nigeria (TETFUND Sponsored)' *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science* (2021) 5(11), 760-768

⁹ F. Agbede, 'Over-Taxed, Under-Served: The Consequences of Over-Taxation in Nigeria by Fope Agbede' https://paper.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5118756 Accessed 11th April, 2025.

¹⁰ See Native Revenue Ordinance Act 1917 and 1928 respectively.

¹¹ Direct Taxation Ordinance. No. 4 of 1940.

¹² Income Tax Management Act, 1940.

1985, 1989, 1990, and 1992. The application of ITMA across regions or states occasioned multiple tax burden on individuals. To put a final nail on the coffin of this problem, two study groups were set up in 1991 of which their recommendation was the enactment of the Personal Income Tax Act¹³ which had nationwide coverage to replace ITMA. The modern day Pay-As-You-Earn system in Nigeria therefore started with the enactment of the Personal Income Tax Act PITA¹⁴, which established the legal framework for the collection of taxes from individuals in Nigeria¹⁵.

3. The Legal and regulatory Framework for Pay-As-You-Earn System in Nigeria

A) Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (As Amended)

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria is the organic law from which all other laws derive their validity¹⁶. The Constitution is supreme and its provisions have binding force on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria¹⁷. The Constitution is vital for taxation because it underscores that no tax regime (including PAYE), can exist validly outside constitutional authorization. Hence, any law or practice regarding PAYE must conform with the provisions of the Constitution or be rendered null and void.

The Constitution establishes a federal structure, distributing taxing powers between the Federal and State Governments through the Legislative Lists in the Second Schedule. The exclusive list empowers only the National Assembly to legislate on matters exclusively reserved for the federal government¹⁸. The Concurrent Legislative List however, includes items that are crucial in understanding how Personal Income Taxation under the PAYE scheme is regulated. It relates to the taxation of incomes, profits, and capital gains¹⁹. It allows both Federal and State Governments to legislate on income taxation, but with clear delineation by specific federal statutes, e.g. Personal Income Tax Act. It also provides to the collection of taxes, including provisions for cooperation between Federal and State tax authorities²⁰. These provisions of the constitution establish the shared jurisdiction for Personal Income Tax in Nigeria and provide the constitutional bedrock for the establishment and operation of the PAYE system.

More so, the tripartite division of power among the Legislature²¹, Executive²², and Judiciary²³ underpins tax governance and enforcement in Nigeria. It empowers the National Assembly to make laws for the peace, order and good government of the federation, particularly on matters in the Exclusive and Concurrent Lists, which include income tax²⁴. It also empowers the state governors and State executive councils to implement State laws, including the administration of PAYE through the State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS)²⁵. The Constitution further grants judicial powers to the courts, which play an essential role in interpreting tax laws, resolving tax disputes, and adjudicating the constitutionality of PAYE procedures and enforcement measures²⁶.

B) Personal Income Tax Act, 1993

¹³ Personal Income Tax Act, 1993.

¹⁴ Personal Income Tax Act, 1993.

¹⁵ A. Odusola, Tax Policy Reforms in Nigeria. Available at <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/63285/1/509144713.pdf> Accessed 11/06/2025

¹⁶ *Famfa Oil Ltd v A.G. Federation and NNPC* (2003) 18NWLR (pt. 852) 453 SC. See also section 1(3) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended).

¹⁷ *Ibid*, s1(1).

¹⁸ *Ibid*, Part I

¹⁹ *Ibid*, Part II Item 7.

²⁰ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (As Amended), Part II Item 7.

²¹ *Ibid*, s4.

²² *Ibid*, s5.

²³ *Ibid*, S6.

²⁴ *Ibid*, s4(2)

²⁵ *Ibid*, s5(2).

²⁶ *Ibdi*, s6.

The Personal Income Tax Act, 1993²⁷ serves as the principal legal framework governing the taxation of individuals in Nigeria, including the regulation and administration of the Pay-As-You-Earn system. The Act, imposes income tax on individuals, communities and families and on executors and trustees, and to provide for the assessment and collection and administration of the tax²⁸.

It mandates every employer to file returns to the relevant tax authority on or before 31st January of each year, showing all emoluments paid to each employee in the previous year²⁹. This ensures transparency and accountability in the administration of PAYE. It also creates a statutory duty for employers as withholding agents. Failure to comply constitutes an offence and attracts penalties. It also requires the employer to pay over to the relevant tax authority the amount deducted, with provisions for payment schedules and modes of remittances. Including electronic channels³⁰.

The Personal Income Act (PITA) prescribes a penalty of 10% of the amount not deducted or remitted, in addition to the actual amount due, as well as potential prosecution under criminal law³¹. This serves as a deterrent to evasion and non-remittance, reinforcing employer accountability. Employees or taxpayers have the right to object to assessments or deductions through a formal process. This ensures taxpayer rights and due process, enhancing fairness in the PAYE tax system³².

The PAYE scheme is applied to the taxable emoluments defined under the Act³³. Taxable income includes, salaries, wages, allowances, benefits in kind, bonuses, gratuities and other income from employment³⁴. The Act provides for Consolidated Relief Allowance which offers relief equal to N200,00 or 1% of gross income plus 20% of the gross income, whichever is higher³⁵. This provision was introduced to simplify personal tax computation and promote equity in the PAYE system.

The Act establishes the State Board of Internal Revenue³⁶ and empowers it to assess, collect, and enforce personal income tax under the PAYE system³⁷. It outlines the structure and administrative mechanisms for the effective implementation of tax collection at the state level. According to the Act, failure to remit deducted tax, or failure to deduct tax at all, attracts penalties, fines, or imprisonment. Employers may also face charges for providing false statements or obstructing tax officers³⁸.

While PITA provides the overall federal framework, most Nigerian states have enacted their own revenue administration laws to operationalize the state Boards of Internal Revenues. These state laws, however, are harmonized with PITA.

C) Federal Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act 2007

The Federal Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act³⁹ is the chief legal instrument in Nigeria's tax administration, providing the structural, administrative, and functional foundation for the operations of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). The Federal Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act (FIRSEA) established the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) as an autonomous agency saddled with tax administration in Nigeria⁴⁰. The FIRS, as

²⁷ Now Personal Income Tax Act (as amended), 2011

²⁸ Ibid, Explanatory Memoranda.

²⁹ Personal Income Tax Act, 1993, s81.

³⁰ Personal Income Tax Act, 1993, s82.

³¹ Ibid

³² Ibid, s83

³³ Ibid, s3 and Sixth Schedule.

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ Ibid, s33.

³⁶ Personal Income Tax Act, 1993, s82.

³⁷ Ibid, s88.

³⁸ Personal Income Tax Act, 1993, s94.

³⁹ Federal Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act, 2007.

⁴⁰ Ibid, s1.

established by this provision, has the legal backing to implement and enforce all laws relating to taxation of individuals and corporate bodies falling under the jurisdiction of the Federal Government.

The Act provides for the functions of the Federal Inland Revenue Service, which includes to assess persons, companies, enterprises chargeable with taxes administered by the Service⁴¹, to collect, recover and pay to the designated account any tax or levy due to the Government⁴², to account for all taxes collected⁴³, and to ensure the effectiveness and optimum collection of all revenue⁴⁴. These provisions empower the Federal Inland Revenue Service to supervise the PAYE system by ensuring that employers deduct appropriate amounts from employees' earnings and remit same to the appropriate tax authorities promptly.

Although the Personal Income Tax Act (PITA), 2011 (as amended) is the principal legislation governing PAYE, the FIRS Establishment Act operationalizes its enforcement, particularly with respect to employers and employees within the federal jurisdiction (e.g., federal institutions, multinational companies, and residents of the Federal Capital Territory). The Act is to the effect that the Service shall conduct investigation and take such necessary action as may be necessary to prevent tax fraud and evasion⁴⁵. This grants the FIRS legal authority to investigate non-compliance with PAYE deductions, such as under-deduction or non-remittance by employers, common evasion techniques that undermine the effectiveness of the PAYE system.

The Act provides for offences and penalties, including failure to deduct or remit tax. An employer who fails to remit PAYE deductions may be criminally liable, with sanctions including fines and imprisonment⁴⁶. These enforcement provisions support the efficacy of the PAYE system by ensuring that deductions are both made and duly remitted.

Furthermore, the Act mandates collaboration with other government agencies. Under the Act, the Service is empowered to collaborate with relevant ministries and agencies to improve tax collection⁴⁷. This provision is particularly significant in PAYE administration, where real-time data sharing with bodies such as the National Identity Management Commission (NIMC) or the National Pension Commission (PenCom) enhances the verification of employment and salary records. Also, it mandates the automation of tax processes, which is vital for digitizing PAYE deductions, monitoring remittances, and closing revenue leakages through non-remittance or manipulation of salary structures⁴⁸.

D) Finance Act, 2020

The Finance Act, 2020 introduced amendments to various tax and fiscal legislations, including the Personal Income Tax Act. It is one of the legal frameworks for the PAYE system in Nigeria.

The Act, introduced the Significant Economic Presence (SEP) rule for Personal Income Tax (PIT) in Nigeria. The idea is that the gains or profits of the trade or business will be taxable in Nigeria when an individual, executor, or trustee outside Nigeria renders professional services to a person resident in Nigeria or a fixed base or agent of a foreign entity in Nigeria⁴⁹.

The Finance Act 2020⁵⁰, also, provides that persons earning the national minimum wage of N30,000 (thirty thousand naira) or lesser monthly are now exempted from Personal Income Tax and are therefore not liable to any Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) deductions in Nigeria.

⁴¹ Ibid, s8 (1)(a).

⁴² Ibid, s8(1)(b).

⁴³ Ibid, s8(1)(c).

⁴⁴ Ibid, s8(1)(d).

⁴⁵ Federal Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act, 2007, s8(1)(m).

⁴⁶ Ibid, Part VI.

⁴⁷ Ibid, s8(1)(g).

⁴⁸ Ibid, s8(1)(q).

⁴⁹ Finance Act, 2020, Section 6A.

⁵⁰ Finance Act, 2020, Section 30 and 33.

The Act further amended section 33 of Personal Income Tax Act (PITA) by modifying the Personal Income Tax relief structure, affecting how Pay-As-You-Earn liabilities are calculated.

4. Administration of Pay-As-You-Earn Tax System in Nigeria

The Pay-As-You-Earn tax system is administered and/or collected by the State Governments which have power to tax individuals or bodies of individuals residing in their territory in a particular year. The relevant State Internal Revenue is by law empowered to collect the taxes on income of individuals, except the following persons who are assessed to tax by the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS): Persons employed by the Nigerian Army, Navy, Airforce, and Police Force, other than in civilian capacity, and officers of the Nigerian Foreign service; every resident of the Federal Capital Territory, and persons not resident in Nigeria who derive income or profit from Nigeria⁵¹.

Pay-As-You-Earn as a component of Personal Income Tax in Nigeria, albeit collected and managed by State tax authorities, is subject to coordination and regulation by federal tax framework, particularly under the Joint Tax Board, a body whose powers and existence are noted in both statutory and constitutional legal instrument. The Personal Income Tax Act empowers the Joint Tax Board to administer the tax throughout Nigeria, and to coordinate its administration while the State Boards of Internal Revenue (SBIR) become saddled with the responsibility of administering the revenue accruing from it.

Although the PAYE system primarily applies to Personal Income Tax (a tax under the jurisdiction of State Board of Internal Revenue Service (SBIRS) in line with the Personal Income Tax Act⁵²),

5. Challenges or Barriers to the Pay-As-You-Earn Tax System in Nigeria

There are so many challenges or barriers to the Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) system in Nigeria. Some of them are:

- a. **Statutory Inconsistency or Inadequate Legislation:** Inconsistencies in statutory provisions is one of the challenges or barriers to the Pay-As-You-Earn system in Nigeria. Inconsistencies in statutory provisions as well as inadequate legislation can actually result to confusion thereby affecting the operation of Pay-As-You-Earn system of taxation in the country.
- b. **Delays or Failure in Remittance by Employers:** Some employers in Nigeria most times refuse or fail to remit the Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) to the government or tax authorities after deducting it from the employees either because of ignorance or intentional evasion. This failure to remit the PAYE by the employers to the tax authorities always lead to loss of revenue for the government, denying it the financial muscle to discharge its constitutional responsibilities.
- c. **Lack of Internet Connectivity:** In most places in Nigeria, there is no reliable internet facility. Apart from limited internet access in some places in Nigeria, there is also low digital literacy rate among the tax authorities and the taxpayers. This lack of access to internet facility and/or low digital literacy rate hinder in no small measure the implementation and practice of the Pay-As-You-Earn system of taxation in Nigeria.
- d. **Lack of Oversight by the Tax Authorities:** There is poor or limited oversight capacity on the part of tax authorities in Nigeria, and this affects the effective implementation and operation of the Pay-As-You-Earn system in the country.
- e. **Lack of Transparency in Tax Assessment:** In Pay-As-You-Earn system, the employees have little or no control in the tax assessment. They have little control over their withholding amounts which can result or occasion over-assessment, or overpayment or underpayment of taxes. There is lack of transparency in the tax assessment system in Nigeria, and this is one of the problems with the PAYE system.
- f. **Poor Taxpayer Education:** There is poor tax education and lack of awareness and/or understanding about the Pay-As-You-Earn system among many Nigerians. For instance, most employees in Nigeria do not know how they PAYE system works. They do not even know or understand how their taxes are deducted and remitted to the tax authorities by the employers. This lack of tax education and/or lack of awareness often leads to mistrust and frustration among employees.

⁵¹ Personal Income Tax Act, 1993, section 2(1)(b).

⁵² Personal Income Tax Act, 1993, section 2(1)(b).

6. Conclusion

There is no doubt that the Pay-As-You-Earn system in Nigeria not only facilitates steady government revenue inflow, but also promotes voluntary tax compliance and enhance tax efficiency. Like every other tax system, the Pay-As-You-Earn system in Nigeria has its fair share of challenges and/or problems as have been identified and discussed in this study above.

To address the challenges, therefore, the following are recommended:

- a. Government of Nigeria should carry out a legislative reform to streamline and make clear laws and policies governing the Pay-As-You-Earn system to ensure fairness and consistency in the system. There should be clear legislations and policies regulating PAYE system.
- b. Awareness creation and tax education should be carried out by tax authorities and government. Employers should be encouraged and educated on the need to remit tax deducted from the incomes of the employees to the tax authorities as and when due. Both the employers and the employees should be educated and informed about the workings of the Pay-As-You-Earn system, the requirements and the gains in compliance.
- c. Government should also ensure that it provides good internet facilities and also embark on capacity building for tax administrators to ensure effective operation of the PAYE system in Nigeria. It should not only provide just access to internet facility to enhance the smooth operation of the PAYE system, but also ensure that taxpayers and tax authorities are well-equipped with the requisite digital training on PAYE management.
- d. The tax authorities should from time to time carry out their oversight function to ensure efficiency in the PAYE system. They should also ensure that there is transparency in tax assessment.